

Ammonium metavanadate an efficient catalyst for Erlenmeyer synthesis

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Abstract : An efficient method to synthesize azalactone derivatives using ammonium metavanadate (NH_4VO_3) as catalyst was performed in the absence of solvent. This method is environmentally friendly and affords the product azalactones in high yields after simple workup.

Keywords : Ammonium metavanadate, solvent free, azalactone, Erlenmeyer, condensation reaction.

Introduction

Heterocyclic compounds occur widely in Nature and are essential to life. In particular, the azalactones exhibit a variety of biological and pharmaceutical properties¹. In nature they are useful precursors for the synthesis of amino acids², peptides³ and synthetically they have been used in the preparation of heterocycles⁴, biosensors⁵ and antitumor or antimicrobial compounds⁶. Thus, the development of facile and environmental friendly synthetic methods for azalactones is currently of great interest. The Erlenmeyer reaction, which is the most widely used method for the preparation of azalactones, involves the direct condensation of aldehydes with hippuric acid in the presence of stoichiometric amounts of fused anhydrous sodium acetate as a basic catalyst in acetic anhydride⁷. Recently, some new reagents have been reported for the synthesis of azalactones, including $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-H}_3\text{BO}_3$ ⁸, supported KF ⁹, $\text{Bi}(\text{OAc})_3$ ¹⁰, $\text{Bi}(\text{OTf})_3$ ¹¹, ZnCl_2 ¹², $\text{Ca}(\text{OAc})_2$ ¹³, $\text{Yb}(\text{OTf})_3$ ¹⁴, $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{HPO}_4$ ¹⁵ and ZnO ¹⁶. Some of these methods, however, suffer from drawbacks, which include the use of hazardous materials¹⁸, materials that are not available or costly^{10,11,14}, long reaction times⁷ and low yields⁹. In this paper we describe the use of ammonium metavanadate as a catalyst in the Erlenmeyer reaction, under solvent-free condition using ultrasonic irradiation.

The application of solvent-free reaction conditions in organic chemistry has been explored extensively within

the last decade. It was shown to be an efficient technique for various organic reactions. Solvent-free conditions often lead to a remarkable decrease in reaction time, increased yields, easier workup, and in some cases enhancement of regio- and stereoselectivity¹⁷.

Ultrasound has increasingly been used in organic synthesis in the recent years. Ultrasonic irradiation enhances the chemical reaction via the process of acoustic cavitation¹⁸. The assistance of ultrasonic irradiation efficiently shortens the reaction times. Simple experimental procedure, very high yields, increased selectivities, and clean reaction of many ultrasound-induced organic transformations offer additional convenience in the field of synthetic organic chemistry¹⁹.

The search continues for a better catalyst in the synthesis of azalactone derivatives in terms of operational simplicity and economic viability. Herein we report the use of ammonium metavanadate (NH_4VO_3) as a water soluble, inorganic acid²⁰ that meets the demand for an economic catalyst. It is employed similar to vanadium pentoxide²¹ and as a catalyst in oxidation reactions with other co-catalysts²². It is a reagent used in analytical chemistry, the photographic industry, and the textile industry²¹. Recently, ammonium metavanadate was found to be effective in the synthesis of octahydroquinazolinone derivatives^{23a}, α -hydroxyphosphonates^{23d}, 2-substituted benzimidazole derivatives. This is the first report of uti-

lizing ammonium metavanadate as a catalyst for the synthesis of azalactone derivatives.

Results and discussion

In continuation of our interest toward the exploitation of NH_4VO_3 as a cheap, readily available and ecofriendly catalyst for the development of new synthetic methodologies in organic synthesis²⁴. We now report a simple and efficient NH_4VO_3 catalyzed synthesis of azalactone derivatives. The transformation involves the reaction of an aldehyde with hippuric acid in the absence of solvent at room temperature under ultrasound irradiation.

In the initial reaction, benzaldehyde and hippuric acid were combined in the presence of 10 mol% of NH_4VO_3 without solvent by grinding the reagents together at ambient temperature. This gave only trace amounts of the desired product (Table 1, entry 1). We then assessed the reaction by grinding the reagents and then heated at 50, 80 and 100 °C affording the product in yields of 65–82% after 90 min (Table 1, entries 2–4). However, the best result was obtained by ultrasound irradiation at ambient temperature affording the product in 95% yield and after only 10 min (Table 1, entry 5).

Table 1. Effect of catalyst on the synthesis of azalactone derivatives **3a**

Entry	Reaction condition	Time (min)	Yield ^a (%)
1	Grinding/r.t.	90	Trace
2	50 °C	90	65
3	80 °C	90	77
4	100 °C	90	82
5	Ultrasound/r.t.	10	95

^aYields refer to pure isolated products.

To determine the optimal catalyst loading required, the ultrasound reaction was repeated with varying amounts of NH_4VO_3 (Table 2). A maximum yield of 95% was obtained with 10 mol% of NH_4VO_3 under ultrasound irradiation. Further increase in catalyst loading to 15

Table 2. Optimization of catalyst loading for synthesis of azalactone derivatives **3a** under solvent free conditions

Entry	NH_4VO_3 (mol%)	Time (min)	Yield ^a (%)
1	0	90	–
2	5	10	78
3	10	10	95
4	15	10	95
5	20	10	94

^aYields of isolated products.

mol%, 20 mol% did not have any significant effect on the yield of product.

The generality of this reaction was examined using a number of aromatic aldehydes, including those bearing electron-withdrawing groups (such as halides and nitro), as well as electron-donating groups (such as methyl, methoxy). In all cases, the reactions gave the corresponding products in good to excellent yield (Table 3). Unfortunately, when an aliphatic aldehyde was tested, none of the desired product was detected (Table 3, compound **3s**). This methodology offers significant improvements with regard to the scope of this transformation, simplicity in operation and green aspects by avoiding expensive or corrosive catalysts.

Ammonium metavanadate acts as an effective catalyst with respect to reaction times and yields, when compared with catalysts known to facilitate this transformation, as shown for the reaction of benzaldehyde with hippuric acid (Table 4).

A mechanism for the action of NH_4VO_3 has been proposed (Scheme 2), whereby the aldehyde carbonyl oxygen binds with the vacant 'd' orbital of vanadium to form complex **1**. This interaction increases the reaction rate tremendously to shorten the overall reaction time.

Experimental

All the reagents and aromatic aldehydes were obtained from commercial suppliers and were not purified. Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. The completion of reactions was monitored by TLC. IR spectra were recorded on KBr matrices with a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer (Manasquan, NJ, USA). ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian Model

Table 3. Erlenmeyer synthesis of azalactone derivatives

Compd.	Aldehydes	Time (min)	Yield ^a (%)	M.p. (°C)	
				Found	Reported
3a	C ₆ H ₅ CHO	10	95	168–170	168–169 ¹⁴
3b	4-MeC ₆ H ₄ CHO	8	92	142–144	143–144 ¹⁴
3c	4-MeOC ₆ H ₄ CHO	10	90	154–156	155–157 ¹⁴
3d	2-ClC ₆ H ₄ CHO	12	94	160–162	159–161 ¹⁴
3e	3-ClC ₆ H ₄ CHO	12	94	152–154	155 ¹⁶
3f	4-ClC ₆ H ₄ CHO	10	96	184–186	186–187 ¹⁴
3g	2-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CHO	10	95	164–166	165–166 ¹⁶
3h	3-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CHO	12	95	166–168	166–167 ¹⁴
3i	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CHO	10	96	240–242	240–241 ¹⁴
3j	N(CH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ CHO	10	92	210–212	210–212 ¹⁶
3k	2,6-(Cl) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ CHO	10	94	162–164	162–163 ¹⁴
3l	2,4-(OCH ₃) ₂ C ₆ H ₃ CHO	10	90	168–170	168–170 ¹⁵
3m	C ₆ H ₅ CH=CH-CHO	15	88	130–132	130–132 ¹⁶
3n	Indole 3-carbaldehyde	10	92	208–210	207–208 ¹⁴
3o	Furfural	8	92	168–170	170 ⁸
3p	Crotonaldehyde	8	85	152–153	152 ⁸
3q	Cyclohexanone	15	85	138–140	139 ⁸
3r	Acetophenone	15	88	104–106	105–106 ¹⁶
3s	Buteraldehyde	40	–	–	–

^aYields of isolated products.

Table 4. Comparison of the results of ammonium metavanadate in the reaction of benzaldehyde, hippuric acid and acetic anhydride with those of other catalysts reported literature

Entry	Catalyst (loading)	Reaction conditions	Time (min)	Yield (%)
1	NH ₄ VO ₃ (10 mol%)	Solvent free, r.t.	10	95 ^a
2	Al ₂ O ₃ -H ₃ BO ₃ (20 mol%)	C ₆ H ₆ /C ₆ H ₅ .CH ₃ , reflux	50	82 ⁸
3	Bi(OAc) ₂ (11 mol%)	C ₂ H ₅ OH, reflux	60	88 ¹⁰
4	Yb(OTf) ₃ (10 mol%)	Solvent free, 40 °C	30	82 ¹⁴
5	(NH ₄) ₂ HPO ₄ (10 mol%)	Solvent free, 80 °C	150	81 ¹⁵
6	ZnO (60 mol%)	C ₂ H ₅ OH, r.t.	10	90 ¹⁶

^aThis work.

Mercury Plus 200 MHz NMR spectrometer (Lake Forest, CA, USA). Mass spectra [ES-MS] were recorded on a Water-Micro Mass Quattro-II spectrometer (Welltech Enterprises, Inc., Capitol Heights, MD, USA). Bandelin Sonorex (35 KHz) ultrasonic bath was used for ultrasonic irradiation.

General procedure for the synthesis of azalactone derivatives (3a-s) :

A dry 50-ml flask was charged with aldehyde (2 mmol), hippuric acid (2.2 mmol), acetic anhydride (6.6 mmol)

and ammonium metavanadate (10 mol%). The mixture was irradiated under ultrasound irradiation at ambient temperature for appropriate time (Table 3). Progress of the reaction was followed by TLC. After completion of the reaction, 5 mL of 95% EtOH was added, and a yellow solid precipitated. The yellow solid was filtered off and washed with hot water. The crude azalactone was recrystallized from acetone/water to afford the pure products.

Spectral data of representative compounds :

4-(Z)-4-Benzylidene-2-phenyloxazol-5(4H)-one (3a) : IR (KBr, ν_{\max}) : 3438, 1796, 1654 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (400

Scheme 2. Proposed mechanism.

MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.28 (1H, s, -CH=), 7.46–7.65 (6H, m, ArH), 8.19–8.24 (4H, m, ArH); MS : m/z 250 (M+H)⁺

4-(Z)-4-(1H-indol-3-yl)methylene)-2-phenyloxazol-5(4H)-one (3n) : IR (KBr, ν_{max}) : 3442, 3230, 1729, 1642, 1170 cm^{-1} ; ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) : δ 7.27–7.28 (2H, t, J 8.0 Hz, ArH), 7.54–7.72 (5H, m, ArH and -CH=), 8.14 (2H, d, J 8.0 Hz, ArH), 8.40 (1H, d, J 8.0 Hz, ArH), 8.64 (1H, s, CH), 12.35 (1H, s, NH); MS : m/z 289 (M+H)⁺.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have developed a general and efficient protocol for the synthesis of azalactone derivatives by condensation of aldehydes with hippuric acid using readily available, inexpensive NH_4VO_3 as catalyst. High yields of the products, short reaction times, mild reaction conditions, simple experimental procedure and product isolation make this protocol complementary to the existing methods.

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